

Table S3. Components of StemCell media expansion and differentiation

Components	Concentration	Supplier
PneumaCult™ Ex-Plus media		StemCell, Cat#05041
PneumaCult™ Ex-Plus media 50x supplement	Unknown	StemCell, Cat#05042
PneumCult™ ALI maintenance media		StemCell, Cat#05002
PneumaCult™-ALI 10x supplement	Unknown	StemCell, Cat#05003
PneumaCult™-ALI maintenance supplement 100x	Unknown	StemCell, Cat#05006
Hydrocortisone		StemCell, Cat#07925
Heparin		StemCell, Cat#07980
Penicillin/streptomycin	2%	Life Tech, Cat#15070-063
Amphotericin B solution	250µg/ml	Sigma, Cat#A2942